

Review: Techniques towards the Plant Phytochemical Study

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Abstract

From ancient history of human evolution and development plants remain always exclusive entity in their life for many purposes. Medicinal and active ingredient remains life supportive things to human and domestic animals. It's always an exclusive field to opens these medicinal and phytochemical ingredients from plants for farther more drug developments. The current review article covers the basic and preliminary technique up to detailed analysis of plants chemical constitutes for many way with many aspects. Desire approach can be possible towards unique phytochemical study with systematic methodology, standard protocol, extraction and analytical techniques.

Key words: *Plant Extractions, Phytochemicals, Chromatography and Solvent.*

Introduction

Nature is a unique source of structures of high phytochemical diversity, many of them possessing interesting biological activities and medicinal properties (Mamta *et al.* 2013). It produced chemical compound found to have large pharmacological and biological activity. Natural products are generally used in drug discovery and drug design (Sharad Visht and Swati Chaturvedi 2012). Approximately 80% people rely on traditional plant based medicines for their initial health care needs in developing countries (Mohammad *et al.* 2014 and Akerele O 1993). The medicinal value of these plants can be observed from the chemical agents they possess which may alter certain physiologic actions in the human body (Gurib-Fakim A 2006 and Hemadri *et al.* 2012). Phytochemical constituents seemed to have potential as source of useful drugs and also to improve

the health status of its users as a result of the presence of various compounds that are vital for good health (Ajayi *et al.* 2011). In addition, the knowledge of the chemical constituents of plants would further be valuable in discovering the actual value of folkloric remedies (Shachi Singh 2012). The medicinal and pharmaceutical properties of plants are due to the type of chemical substance they produce and store (Jain *et al.* 2013). These include compounds that are utilized as food by man and other animals and also other compounds that exert physiological effects on them. This second group of chemical substances often referred to as secondary metabolites, gives plants their therapeutic properties (Yusuf *et al.* 2014). Plant metabolites were mainly investigated from a phytochemical and chemotaxonomic viewpoint during this period. Over the last decade, however, interest in drugs of plant and probably animal origin has grown steadily (Hamburger M and Hostettmann K 1991) Plants have an extraordinary ability to synthesize various substances and metabolites (Mudasir *et al.* 2012). Plants in all facet of life have served a valuable starting material for drug development (Edeoga *et al.* 2005). So these natural compounds formed the base of modern drugs as we use today (Rout *et al.* 2009). However in recent years, Phytochemicals or secondary plant metabolites have been extensively investigated as a source of medicinal agents (Krishnaraju *et al.* 2005).

Basically Phytochemicals deals with chemicals obtained from the plant and also a most important areas of nutrition research today (Karthishwaran *et al.* 2010). Phytochemicals accumulate in different parts of the plants, such as in the roots, stems, leaves, flowers, fruits or seeds (Costa *et al.* 1999). The word Phyto means “plant” in Greek, implying that these chemicals are found in plants. Scientists who study these naturally occurring substances are coming up with some very interesting findings. Apparently, phytochemicals have a wide variety health benefits, including protection of the heart.

Actual and Exact classification of phytochemicals could not been performed so far, because of the wide variety of them all (Mamta *et al.* 2013). In resent year Phytochemicals are asbroadlyclassified into two groups, i.e. primary and secondary constituents; according to their functions in plant metabolism. Primary constituents comprises common sugars, amino acid, proteins and chlorophyll while secondary constituents consists of alkaloids, terpenoids, steroids and flavonoids, so on (Dhawale PG. 2013).They are originally known to accumulate under defense response; against abiotic, biotic and insect stress. It is believed that plants had to accumulate new

secondary constituents during evolution for their protection. Secondary metabolites are important source of pharmaceuticals for human use. There are literally thousands of phytochemicals and only a relatively small percentage has been analyzed so far. What we can say with reasonable certainty, however, is that a diet rich in plant foods (fruits, vegetables, whole grains, beans, seeds and nuts) have significant amount of these chemicals.

WORKING WITH PHYTOMICALS

Selection of plant Material: Generally plant selection involves a deep literature survey of the floristic diversity. Selection of plant material is performed by different approaches, like it may be totally random selection, specific selection using ethno pharmacological reports or may be restricting the plants of interest to group based on chemotaxonomic, geographical, or compound structural - type of preferences.

Collection: - During collection of plant, it should be kept in mind that the specimens to be studied should be healthy.

Factors Influencing on Extractions:-Some of the factors that affect the concentration levels and kinds of phytochemicals and secondary metabolites are site altitude, plant age, climate, soil type, time of collection, species etc. Chemical composition of herms also varies depending on species and environmental factors (Dermarderosian A. 2001 and Sharad Visht & Swati Chaturvedi 2012).

Identification and authentication:-After collection, the plant material should be identified or authenticated by a taxonomist. At least three specimens should be prepared. One of these samples should be deposited in a local national herbarium, and the others should be deposited in a specialist museum or herbarium and kept in an appropriate protected place for future reference (Sharad Visht & Swati Chaturvedi 2012 and Stahl Egon 2005).

Different Solvent systems:-Usually secondary metabolites have different degree of polarity so the solvent should be chosen for extraction chosen carefully to ensure dissolution of secondary metabolites. Properties of a good solvent in plant extractions includes, low toxicity, ease of evaporation at low heat, promotion of rapid physiologic absorption of the extract, preservative action, inability to cause the extract to complex or dissociate.

SOLVENT SELECTION

The basic knowledge of nature and characteristics of phytoconstituents is essential to select method and solvent for extraction. Nature of phytoconstituents involves polarity, pH, thermostability etc. The factors affecting the choice of solvent are quantity of phytochemicals to be extracted, rate of extraction, diversity of different compounds extracted, diversity of inhibitory compounds extracted, ease of subsequent handling of the extracts, toxicity of the solvent in the bioassay process, potential health hazard of the extractants.

1. Water: Water is universal solvent, used to extract plant products with antimicrobial activity. Though traditional healers use primarily water but plant extracts from organic solvents have been found to give more consistent antimicrobial activity compared to water extract. Also water soluble flavonoids (mostly anthocyanins) have no antimicrobial significance and water soluble phenolic only important as antioxidant compound.

2. Acetone: Acetone dissolves many hydrophilic and lipophilic components from the two plants used, is miscible with water, is volatile and has a low toxicity to the bioassay used, it is a very useful extractant (Udaya *et al.* 2013), especially for antimicrobial studies where more phenolic compounds are required to be extracted.

3. Alcohol: The higher activity of the ethanolic extracts as compared to the aqueous extract can be attributed to the presence of higher amounts of polyphenols as compared to aqueous extracts. It means that they are more efficient in cell walls and seeds degradation which have unpolar character and cause polyphenols to be released from cells. More useful explanation for the decrease in activity of aqueous extract can be ascribed to the enzyme polyphenol oxidase, which degrade polyphenols in water extracts, whereas in methanol and ethanol they are inactive (Muhammad *et al.* 2012). Moreover, water is a better medium for the occurrence of the microorganisms as compared to ethanol. The higher concentrations of more bioactive flavonoid compounds were detected with ethanol 70% due to its higher polarity than pure ethanol. By adding water to the pure ethanol up to 30% for preparing ethanol 70% the polarity of solvent was increased. Additionally, ethanol was found easier to penetrate the cellular membrane to extract the intracellular ingredients from the plant material. Since nearly all of the identified components from plants active against microorganisms are aromatic or saturated organic compounds, they are most

often obtained through initial ethanol or methanol extraction (Phillipson J. David 2000). Methanol is more polar than ethanol but due to its cytotoxic nature, it is unsuitable for extraction in certain kind of studies as it may lead to incorrect results.

4. Chloroform: Terpenoid lactones have been obtained by successive extractions of dried barks with hexane, chloroform and methanol with activity concentrating in chloroform fraction. Occasionally tannins and terpenoids will be found in the aqueous phase, but they are more often obtained by treatment with less polar solvents (Balendra Sing and Sharad Kumar Yadav 2010).

5. Ether: Ether is commonly used selectively for the extraction of coumarins and fatty acids (Phillipson J. David 2000).

6. Dichloromethanol: It is another solvent used for carrying out the extraction procedures. It is specially used for the selective extraction of only terpenoids (Thota E L 2010).

Table : Solvents used for active component extraction

Water	Ethanol	Methanol	Chloroform	Ether	Acetone
Anthocyanins	Tannins	Anthocyanins	Terpenoids	Alkaloids	Phenol
Starches	Polyphenols	Terpenoids	Flavonoids	Terpenoids	Flavonols
Tannins	Polyacetylenes	Saponins		Coumarins	
Saponins	Flavonol	Tannins		Fatty acids	
Terpenoids	Terpenoids	Xanthoxylines			
Polypeptides	Sterols	Totarol			
Lectins	Alkaloids	Quassinoids			
		Lactones			
		Flavones			

PLANT EXTRACTION METHODS:-

There is no single perfect method for extraction, purification and isolation of compound. The first fractionation step is general extraction of secondary metabolite which is done either by using single „all-purpose“ solvents such as methanol or by using petroleum ether to defat the material. Methanol dissolves most of the secondary metabolites and enhancing their release from

cellular matrix/cell surface. Filtration or centrifugation is the first basic technique used to separate insoluble material and filtrate that contain dissolved secondary metabolite. The choice of extraction procedure and extraction solvent depends on the physicochemical nature of secondary metabolite, nature of plant material (fresh parts, dried parts) and their physical state. Selection of extraction method depends on Nature of component, Nature of material to be use and Solvent system available. Based on material which one selecting they can as follows.

a. Plant tissue homogenization: Plant tissue homogenization in solvent has been widely used by researchers. Dried or wet, fresh plant parts are grinded in a blender to fine particles, put in a certain quantity of solvent and shaken vigorously for 5 - 10 min or left for 24 h after which the extract is filtered. The filtrate then may be dried under reduced pressure and re-dissolved in the solvent to determine the concentration. Some researchers however centrifuged the filtrate for clarification of the extract.

b. Serial exhaustive extraction: It is another common method of extraction which involves successive extraction with solvents of increasing polarity from a non-polar (hexane) to a more polar solvent (methanol) to ensure that a wide polarity range of compound could be extracted.

c. Soxhlet extraction: Soxhlet extraction is only required where the desired compound has a limited solubility in a solvent, and the impurity is insoluble in that solvent. If the desired compound has a high solubility in a solvent then a simple filtration can be used to separate the compound from the insoluble substance (Bohlin L 1998). The advantage of this system is that instead of many portions of warm solvent being passed through the sample, just one batch of solvent is recycled. This method cannot be used for thermolabile compounds as prolonged heating may lead to degradation of compounds.

d. Maceration: Maceration is the process by which the plant material is left to 'soak' in a solvent or oil carrier. This may take days, weeks, or months, depending on the concentration of essential oil desired and of course the plant material from which the essential oil is being extracted. It is a very simple process, and can be used at home to make your own Infused Oils. Commercially, when this method is used, a similar distillation process to that described in the Effleurage method is used to extract the essential oil from the solvent or carrier oil base.

e. Distillation: The Distillation method is used where the oils adhere so strongly to the plant material that steam heat must be used to separate them, e.g. as in eucalyptus oil extraction, or where the essential oil content of the plant is so minute that a stronger method of extraction must be used so that all the essential oil content in the plant material can be obtained. In the Distillation process steam is passed over the leaves or flowers and the essential oil evaporates off the plant material with the steam. As the steam cools down, it turns back into water which is collected in a collecting vessel, and the essential oil settles on top of this. Being lighter than water, the essential oils can be either skimmed off the surface of the water, or can be very easily tapped off.

f. Decoction: this method is used for the extraction of the water soluble and heat stable constituents from crude drug by boiling it in water for 15 minutes, cooling, straining and passing sufficient cold water through the drug to produce the required volume (Bohlin L 1998).

g. Infusion: It is a dilute solution of the readily soluble components of the crude drugs. Fresh infusions are prepared by macerating the solids for a short period of time with either cold or boiling water.

h. Digestion: This is a kind of maceration in which gentle heat is applied during the maceration extraction process. It is used when moderately elevated temperature is not objectionable and the solvent efficiency of the men strum is increased.

i. Percolation: This is the procedure used most frequently to extract active ingredients in the preparation of tinctures and fluid extracts. A percolator (a narrow, cone-shaped vessel open at both ends) is generally used. The solid ingredients are moistened with an appropriate amount of the specified men strum and allowed to stand for approximately 4 h in a well closed container, after which the mass is packed and the top of the percolator is closed. Additional men strum is added to form a shallow layer above the mass, and the mixture is allowed to macerate in the closed percolator for 24 h. The outlet of the percolator then is opened and the liquid contained therein is allowed to drip slowly.

j. Sonication: The procedure involves the use of ultrasound with frequencies ranging from 20 kHz to 2000 kHz; this increases the permeability of cell walls and produces cavitation. Although the process is **useful in some cases**, like extraction of rauwolfia root, its large-scale application is limited due to the higher costs. One disadvantage of the procedure is the occasional but known

deleterious effect of ultrasound energy (more than 20 kHz) on the active constituents of medicinal plants through formation of free radicals and consequently undesirable changes in the drug molecules.

ANALYSIS METHODS

Primary Phytochemical analysis:- Phytochemical tests were done to find the presence of the active chemical constituents such as alkaloid, saponins, terpenoid, flavonoids, triterpenes, phenolic, tannins etc, compounds and by the following procedure Phytochemical examinations were carried out for all the extracts as per the standard methods.

Alkaloids:-Wagner's test (Mohammad *et al.* 2014): addition of wagner's reagent to the filtrate results in formation of reddish brown precipitate indicating the presence of alkaloids. **Hager's test** (Mohammad *et al.* 2014): filtrates were treated with hager's reagent. Formation of yellow coloured precipitate indicates positive test.

Anthraquinones :-Borntrager's test (for free anthracene derivatives) (Yusuf *et al.* 2014): the powdered leaves (0.5 g) was taken in a test tube and 5 ml of chloroform was added and shaken for 5 min. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate shaken with equal volume of 10% ammonia solution. A pink, red or violet colour in the aqueous layer after shaken indicates the presence of free anthraquinone (evans, 2002).

Cardiac glycosides :-Keller killiani test(Mohammad *et al.* 2014, Kangogo *et al.* 2014, Dinesh *et al.* 2013) to the 2 ml of extract, 1ml of glacial acetic acid and a few drops of FeCl₃ were added and concentrated H₂SO₄ added from the sides of test tube, green, blue precipitate shows the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Coumarins:- (Dinesh *et al.* 2013) To the 2 ml of extract, 3 ml of 10% naoh was appearance of yellow colour indicates presence of coumarins.

Flavonoids:-Sodium hydroxide test (Yusuf *et al.* 2014) when in extracts 2 mls of 10% naoh solution was added, yellow solution indicates the presence of flavonoids which on adding dilute hydrochloric acid becomes colourless (evans, 2002).**Lead acetate test:** (Mohammad *et al.* 2014)

extracts were treated with few drops of lead acetate solution. Formation of yellow coloured precipitate indicates the presence of flavonoids.

Glycosides:- (Dinesh *et al.* 2013) Extract was hydrolysed by hcl and neutralized with naoh followed by addition of Fehling's solution a and b in 1:1 proportion, produces a red precipitate, indicating presence of glycosides.

Phenols:- (Kangogo *et al.* 2014) Five ml of the extract was dissolved in distilled water. To this solution, 3 ml of 10% lead acetate solution was added. A dark-green colour indicated the presence of phenolic compounds.

Reducing sugars:- Fehling's test (Dinesh *et al.* 2013) Extract shaken with distilled water and filtered, it was boiled on the addition of fehling's solution a and b in equal quantity, appearance of orange red precipitate positively detects reducing sugars.

Saponins:-Frothing test(Kangogo *et al.* 2014, Yusuf *et al.* 2014 and Dharmendra *et al.* 2012): the powdered leaves (0.5 g) was placed in a test tube and 10 ml of distilled water was added and shaken vigorously for 30 s. It was then allowed to stand for 30 min and observed. Formation of honey comb froth indicates the presence of saponins. Haemolysistest (Yusuf *et al.* 2014): one gram of the leaves was extracted with distilled water and 2 ml of aqueous NaCl solution was placed in a test tube and 2 ml of the filtrate was added to the test tube. Then 3 drops of an animal blood was added to the tube by means of a syringe and mixed gently by inverting the tube (no shaking) and allowed to stand for 15 min. The settling down of the red blood cells denotes the presence of saponins.

Steroids:-Salkowski's test: (Mohammad *et al.* 2014, Yusuf *et al.* 2014 and Dharmendra *et al.* 2012) 2 ml of extracts were treated with 2 ml chloroform and filtered. Filtrates were treated with few drops of concentrated H₂SO₄, shaken and allowed to stand. Appearance of golden yellow color interface indicates the presence of steroid ring. Liebermann burchard's test: (Mohammad *et al.* 2014, Kangogo *et al.* 2014 and Yusuf *et al.* 2014) extracts were treated with chloroform and filtered. Filtrates were treated with few drops of acetic anhydride, boiled and cooled. Concentrated H₂SO₄ was added. The reagents, acetic anhydride and concentrated H₂SO₄ react with the hydroxyl

group of phytosterols to produce a dark green color in the upper layer and red color in the lower layer indicating the presence of steroids.

Tannin :-Ferric chloride test(Mohammad *et al.* 2014, Yusuf *et al.* 2014 and 33) three drops of diluted solution of FeCl_3 was added to the test tube , production of a blue or greenish-black colour that changes to olive green as more ferric chloride is added indicates the presence of tannins.

Triterpenes:- Lieberman-burchard's reaction: (Mohammad *et al.* 2014, Kangogo *et al.* 2014and Yusuf *et al.* 2014)extracts were treated with chloroform and filtered. Filtrates were treated with few drops of acetic anhydride, boiled and cooled. Concentrated H_2SO_4 was added. The reagents, acetic anhydride and concentrated H_2SO_4 react with the hydroxyl group of phytosterols to produce a dark green color in the upper layer and red color in the lower layer indicating the presence of triterpenes.

ISOLATION METHODS

Fractionation: All separation processes involve the division of a mixture into a number of discrete fractions. These fractional may be physically discrete fraction. In which successive partition into diethyl ether, chloroform and ethyl acetate will often afford in turn flavonones and flavonols, methoxylated flavonoids and flavonoid monoglycosides. Di- and polyglycosylated flavonoids will remain in the residual aqueous phase. Saponins are water soluble compounds, and the crude saponin fractions are water soluble compounds, and the crude saponin fractions may be obtained. The alkaloids are basic compounds may be extracted either into aqueous acid solution after removal of neutral impurities with an organic solvent, or by treating the groups wet plant material with an alkaline substance such as CaCO_3 powder and extracting with diethyl ether after standing overnight. Specific literature should be consulted for specific plant extraction problems.

Sublimation is used for isolation of caffeine from tea, for its purification of materials present in a crude extract and for separation of camphor.

Distillation is much used to isolate volatile oils and hydrocyanic acid form plant material. The TAS oven is used for steam distillation on a semi micro scale for the direct transfer of volatile materials from a powdered drug to thin layer plate (Rastogi RP and Mehrotra BN 1999).

Fractional liberation, heresome compounds are separated by fractional liberation from a mixture. A mixture of alkaloid salts in aqueous solution, when treated with aliquots of alkali, will give first

the weakest base in the free salt followed by base liberation in ascending order of basicity. If the mixture is shaken with an organic solvent after each addition, then a fractionated series of base will be obtained. A similar procedure is used for organic acids soluble in water immiscible solvents. In this case, starting with a mixture of the acid salts, it is possible to fractionally liberate the acids by addition of mineral acids. Sodium salts of acids on treatment with dilute HCl yield free organic acids.

ANALYTICAL TECHNIQUE

The spots of thin-layer and paper chromatograms are usually revealed by UV fluorescence at certain characteristic wavelengths, before or after the treatment with an aqueous-ethanol solution of potassium hydroxide or with ammonia vapor, or using some other color reaction (Tosun *et al.* 2008).

Thin-layer chromatography (TLC): The oldest publications recommended one- or two- thin layer chromatography for separation and identification. This method provides a quite rapid separation of components in a sample mixture. Fractions obtained from column chromatography were usually checked with the use of TLC technique (Tosun *et al.* 2008). Thin-layer chromatography gives the possibility of performing multi-dimensional separation – two-dimensional separation with the use of the same stationary phase, with different mobile phases (Gadzikowska *et al.*, 2005; Härmälä *et al.*, 1990; Waksmundzka-Hajnos *et al.*, 2006). In TLC, there are almost no limits as far as mobile phases are concerned, because they can be easily evaporated from the layer after the development in the first dimension. Both methods, use of the same layer and different mobile phases or two different layers developed with two mobile phases, make use of different selectivity to achieve complete separation in the two-dimensional process (Faisal *et al.* 2011). The largest differences are obtained with a normal phase system, with an adsorption mechanism of separation, and a reversed-phase system, with a partition mechanism of separation, are applied for two-dimensional separations (Nyireddy, 2001). Two-dimensional thin-layer chromatography with adsorbent gradient is an effective method for the separation of large group of substances present in natural mixtures, e.g. plant extracts (Khan PA and Hajare MV 2014a).

Column Chromatography (CC): The good results for purification, separation of the total furanocoumarins and the isolation of individual compounds give column chromatography (CC) a significant advantage of the use of various sorbents and solvent systems.

Gas Chromatography (GC): In the recent decade, tasks related to the isolation of furocoumarins and the quality controls of related preparations were most frequently solved using GC techniques. Gas chromatography was predominantly used for the identification and quantitative analysis of furocoumarins in preparations and raw plant materials. Investigations of the chromatographic behavior (retention times) of substituted furocoumarins revealed the following general laws: 1) on passage from hydroxy- to methoxycoumarins, the retention time decreases (because of reduced adsorption via hydrogen bonds); 2) furocoumarins with O-alkyl substituents at C5 are eluted after 8-hydroxy isomers; 3) the logarithm of the relative retention time is a linear function of the molecular weight. This GC data can be used for determining the structure and estimating the retention time of analogous coumarins (Lozhkin, AV and Sakanyan EI 2006). A number of methods have been described for the analysis of furanocoumarins using capillary gas chromatography (GC) (Beier RC and Oertli EH 1983).

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC): is an important tool for the analysis of phytochemicals and for drug monitoring. It is used for chemistry and biochemistry research analyzing complex mixtures, purifying chemical compounds, developing processes for synthesizing chemical compounds, isolating natural products, or predicting physical properties. It is also used in quality control to ensure the purity of raw materials, to control and improve process yields, to quantify assays of final products, or to evaluate product stability and monitor degradation (Khan PA and Hajare MV 2014b).

High Performance Thin- Layer Chromatography (HPTLC): Is a visual technique where the “chromatogram” is “visible”. This gives us additional information and confidence in the results. The chromatogram i.e. the separated sample after chromatography can be inspected. (Nehete Jeetendra *et al.* 2009)

For farther structural identification and characterizing of the compounds, especially use of, instrumental techniques such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy and infrared spectroscopy (IR) are used. NMR spectroscopy is an invaluable technique for the structural

determination (Ivanova *et al.* 2003 and Saoussen *et al.* 2010). As well as providing information on the chemical environment of each proton or carbon nucleus in the molecule, the technique can be employed to determine linkages amongst nearby nuclei, often enabling a complete structure to be assembled (Rice-Evans CA and Packer L 2003 and KinukoIwasa *et al.* 2008).

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